

1 **Chance and necessity in the assembly of plant communities:**
2 **stochasticity increases with size, isolation, and diversity of**
3 **temporary ponds**

4 Matías Arim^{*, ϕ ,a}, Verónica Pinelli ^{ϕ ,a}, Lucía Rodríguez-Tricot^a, Esteban
5 Ortiz^a, Mariana Illarze^a, César Fagúndez-Pachón^a, Ana I. Borthagaray^a

6 a.- Departamento de Ecología y Gestión Ambiental, Centro Universitario Regional del
7 Este (CURE), Universidad de la República, Tacuarembó s/n, Maldonado, Uruguay, ZIP:
8 20100.

9

10 * Corresponding author: matiasarim@gmail.com, arim@fcien.edu.uy

11 ϕ Equal authorships

12 **Abstract**

13 1. Biodiversity emerges from niche mechanisms, in which the combination of traits
14 determines species performance, and populations drift because of the inherent
15 stochasticity of community assembly processes. Population biology dictates that small
16 and isolated communities are more prone to show stochastic assemblages. However, a
17 reduced mass effect in isolated communities may promote trait selection. In addition,
18 large and connected communities have a larger species pool, higher functional
19 redundancy, lower population sizes, and more random recruitment, which also fosters
20 stochasticity in community assembly. These contradictory expectations demand
21 empirical analyses.

22 2. Plant metacommunities in temporary ponds are assembled by the action of strong
23 environmental filters and cover wide ranges of local community sizes and connectivity,
24 representing ideal systems for identifying determinants of trait-selection processes.
25 Using a deviance partition method introduced by the theory of community assembly by
26 traits selection (CATS), we evaluated the role of plant traits in local community
27 assemblies along 60 communities from a 14-year plant survey of temporary ponds.

28 3. Variation in pond size, hydroperiod, connectivity, and heterogeneity determined a
29 selection gradient in traits related to drought resistance, life history, and dispersal
30 strategies; but also in the strength of trait-mediated community assembly. The
31 taxonomic and functional diversity of a pond and its physical heterogeneity fostered
32 stochasticity in the assembly of the community, which also presented a hump-shaped
33 association with connectivity. The pond area increased taxonomic richness but
34 decreased functional diversity, determining negative and positive indirect effects on
35 stochasticity.

36 4. Synthesis. Diversity provides the raw material for trait-selection putatively reducing
37 stochasticity, but here diversity was positively related to stochasticity. Having enough
38 functional diversity, larger redundancy, and lower population sizes in diverse
39 communities is probably fostering stochastic assemblages. The hump-shaped
40 association between stochasticity and connectivity supports a larger role of trait
41 selection in isolated systems due to a weak mass effect, but also on connected
42 communities in which a set of more optimal traits for the selection scenario could be
43 available. In the ongoing state of ecosystem fragmentation, these empirical trends
44 contribute to the mechanistic understanding of the connection between landscape
45 structure and biodiversity assembly.

46

47

48 **Resumen**

49 1. La biodiversidad emerge por la acción de mecanismos de nicho, en donde la
50 combinación de rasgos determina el desempeño de las especies, y por la deriva en
51 abundancias debido a la naturaleza estocástica de los procesos de ensamblaje de
52 comunidades. La biología de poblaciones indica que las comunidades aisladas y
53 pequeñas son más propensas a presentar ensamblajes estocásticos. Sin embargo, en
54 comunidades aisladas, la reducción del efecto de masa puede promover un mayor papel
55 de la selección de rasgos. Asimismo, comunidades grandes y conectadas presentan
56 pooles de especies más grandes, mayor redundancia funcional, menor tamaño
57 poblacional y reclutamientos más aleatorios, promoviendo la estocasticidad en el
58 ensamblaje de las comunidades. Estas predicciones contradictorias demandan avanzar
59 en estudios empíricos.

60 2. Las metacomunidades de plantas en charcos temporales son ensambladas por la
61 acción de fuertes filtros ambientales y abarcan amplios gradientes de tamaño y
62 conectividad en sus comunidades locales. Representan así sistemas ideales para
63 identificar los determinantes de los procesos de selección de rasgos. Utilizando métodos
64 de partición de deviance propuestos por la teoría de Ensamblaje de Comunidades por
65 Selección de Rasgos (CATS-por su silga en inglés), evaluamos los determinantes de los
66 patrones de selección y de la fuerza de la estocasticidad en el ensamblaje de especies de
67 plantas en 60 comunidades monitoreadas por 14 años.

68 3. El tamaño de los charcos, su hidroperíodo, conectividad y heterogeneidad
69 determinaron un gradiente de selección de rasgos asociados a la resistencia a la sequía,
70 historia de vida y estrategia de dispersión; pero también en la importancia total de los
71 procesos de ensamblaje de especies mediados por rasgos. La diversidad taxonómica y
72 funcional de un charco y su heterogeneidad promovieron la estocasticidad en el

73 ensamblaje, la cual también presentó un patrón en joroba con la conectividad. El área
74 del charco aumentó la diversidad taxonómica pero redujo la diversidad funcional,
75 determinando efectos indirectos positivos y negativos sobre la estocasticidad.

76 4. Síntesis. La diversidad provee el material para la selección de rasgos, esperándose
77 que reduzca la estocasticidad en el ensamblaje de especies. Sin embargo, la diversidad
78 se asoció positivamente con la estocasticidad. Una vez que se tiene suficiente diversidad
79 funcional, la alta redundancia y los menores tamaños poblacionales probablemente
80 promueven procesos aleatorios de ensamblaje. La relación en joroba entre
81 estocasticidad y aislamiento sustenta un papel más importante de la selección de rasgos
82 en comunidades aisladas, probablemente debido a la reducción del efecto de masa, pero
83 también en las comunidades más conectadas, en donde combinaciones de rasgos más
84 apropiados para el escenario de selección pueden estar disponibles. En la tendencia
85 actual de fragmentación de ecosistemas, los patrones empíricos acá reportados
86 contribuyen a una comprensión mecanicista de la conexión entre estructura del paisaje y
87 en ensamblaje de la biodiversidad.

88

89 **Keywords:** biodiversity, CATS, community assembly, drift, functional diversity,
90 isolation, landscape, stochasticity, trait selection.

91 **1. INTRODUCTION**

92 The relative importance of niche and neutral processes in community assembly has been
93 extensively debated (Tilman 2004; Gravel *et al.* 2006; Holyoak & Loreau 2006; Leibold
94 & McPeck 2006; Ai *et al.* 2013; Munoz & Huneman 2016; Leibold *et al.* 2019;
95 Mitchell *et al.* 2019; Laroche *et al.* 2020; Siqueira *et al.* 2020a). If species traits do not
96 affect their performance, then the community is neutrally assembled, and stochastic
97 trait-independent drift in the relative abundance of species is expected (Hubbell 2001).
98 The assembly of communities by niche mechanisms, in which species are selected in
99 the assembly processes based on their traits, is a force in opposition to stochasticity,
100 leading to a more deterministic species composition in communities (Shipley 2010;
101 Vellend 2016). It should be noted that while traits bias the success of species in a
102 community, this is also a random process in which stochasticity is still determining
103 species abundances (Shipley 2010; Vellend 2016). However, the stronger the trait
104 selection—niche assembly—the lower the stochastic drift in abundance will be (Shipley
105 2010; Vellend 2016).

106 Theoretical studies indicate that community size and isolation are the main
107 determinants of the relative importance of trait selection and drift in community
108 assembly. However, both positive and negative effects could be expected. Population
109 genetics and population ecology hold that small and isolated communities are more
110 prone to show drift in abundances and, consequently, more closely resemble neutral
111 assembly patterns (Adler, HilleRisLambers & Levine 2007; Orrock & Watling 2010;
112 Fukami 2015; Gilbert & Levine 2017; Siqueira *et al.* 2020a). In large and connected
113 communities, the large number of individuals reduces the stochasticity of random
114 processes (Orrock & Watling 2010; Fisher & Mehta 2014; Siqueira *et al.* 2020a) and
115 the increase in functional diversity may enhance the role of niche mechanisms (Shipley

116 2010; Enquist *et al.* 2015). This is because trait selection requires functional diversity to
117 play its role in community assembly. Without variation in traits, selection cannot affect
118 species abundances (Shipley 2010).

119 In contrast to previous arguments, other mechanisms can promote a larger role
120 of traits in small and isolated communities and of stochasticity in large and central
121 communities. Species richness increases with community size, and different
122 mechanisms may be beyond a positive stochasticity-richness association, such as the
123 increase in priority effect (Chase 2010), functional redundancy (Shipley 2010), lower
124 average population sizes (Fukami 2015), neutral aggregations (Scheffer & van Nes
125 2006) and a larger species pool for recruitment that reinforces previous mechanisms. In
126 fact, at least on a global scale, a positive association between drift and total richness has
127 been reported in forest plots (Leibold & Chase 2018). Furthermore, if heterogeneity
128 increases with area and/or the opposite occurs with disturbances, then attenuation of
129 environmental filters reduces the strength of trait selection favouring stochasticity in
130 community assembly (Cadotte & Tucker 2017). On the other hand, dispersal limitation
131 by isolation can enhance trait selection when only species with high dispersal abilities
132 are able to reach isolated communities (Ai *et al.* 2013). A smaller number of incoming
133 dispersers also reduces the role of mass effects, resulting in a closer connection between
134 species traits and performance (Leibold *et al.* 2004; Ai *et al.* 2013; Borthagaray *et al.*
135 2015; Leibold *et al.* 2019). In summary, the relative importance of the niche and neutral
136 assembly of a community may systematically change along gradients of community size
137 and isolation, with species richness and functional diversity playing core roles in these
138 trends, but having contrasting theoretical expectations. In this context, presenting
139 empirical analyses is the essential step for advancing theoretical constructions (Marquet
140 *et al.* 2014; Grainger *et al.* 2022).

141 Empirical studies have indirectly considered the role of traits or drift in
142 community assembly. Methods have included fitting to diversity distributions (Hubbell
143 2001; Fisher & Mehta 2014), partitioning of variance (Gilbert & Lechowicz 2004;
144 Brown *et al.* 2017; Bosc *et al.* 2019), multivariate ordination for visualizing trait-
145 environment associations (Legendre & Legendre 1998), and contrasting with null
146 models (Chase 2010; Chase & Myers 2011; Tucker *et al.* 2016; Siqueira *et al.* 2020a).
147 Recently, novel methods for the direct analysis of the role of traits in community
148 assembly have been proposed (Shipley 2010; Brown *et al.* 2014; Dray *et al.* 2014;
149 Shipley 2014b; Peres-Neto, Dray & ter Braak 2017; Keddy & Laughlin 2021). Among
150 them, the methodology introduced in the theory of community assembly by trait
151 selection (CATS) provides a direct evaluation of the role of traits in species
152 performance and of the role stochasticity in community assembly (Shipley, Vile &
153 Garnier 2006; Shipley 2010; Shipley, Paine & Baraloto 2012; Shipley 2014a; Loranger
154 *et al.* 2018; Cunillera-Montcusí *et al.* 2020).

155 Ephemeral environments impose a strong selection regimen for species survival
156 in changing environmental conditions (Cunillera-Montcusí *et al.* 2020). Temporary
157 ponds frequently conform metacommunities with large gradients in local community
158 sizes, isolations, hydroperiod regimens, local heterogeneities (Srivastava *et al.* 2004;
159 Richardson *et al.* 2022) and spatial gradients that were related to community structure in
160 empirical studies (Arim *et al.* 2010; Arim *et al.* 2011; Borthagaray, Berazategui & Arim
161 2015; Cunillera-Montcusí *et al.* 2020; Rodriguez-Tricot & Arim 2020). Therefore, the
162 nature and strength of trait-mediated community assembly versus stochastic drift is
163 expected to systematically change along these gradients (Cunillera-Montcusí *et al.*
164 2020). For these reasons, metacommunities of temporary ponds conform suitable
165 models for the empirical analysis of metacommunity assembly mechanisms (Srivastava

166 *et al.* 2004). Here, we focus on a 14-year survey in which the occurrences of 100 plant
167 species in 60 temporary ponds were recorded. These ponds cover a wide range of
168 connectivity and local conditions, showing a large species turnover between ponds
169 (Arim *et al.* 2011; Canavero *et al.* 2014; Piñeiro-Guerra *et al.* 2014; Borthagaray,
170 Berazategui & Arim 2015; Rodriguez-Tricot & Arim 2020). This pattern supports a
171 putative role for trait-mediated species filtering and trait-mediated dispersal effects on
172 community assembly.

173 In the present study, we focus on this plant metacommunity to evaluate the
174 hypothesized determinants of the relative importance of stochastic versus niche-based
175 processes in community assembly. Explicitly, the following hypotheses were
176 considered (Figure 1): *Hypothesis 1*: the size of the community, the number of
177 individuals from all species combined, increases the taxonomic and functional diversity
178 of communities because it allows for a greater number of species with viable
179 populations (Storch, Bohdalková & Okie 2018). As the size of the community is
180 proportional to the area of the pond (Berazategui 2012), the taxonomic and functional
181 diversity should increase with this variable. *Hypothesis 2*: Functional diversity increases
182 the strength of trait selection in community assembly because the differences in traits
183 between species is the raw material for the action of selection on community assembly
184 (Shipley 2010; Enquist *et al.* 2015). *Hypothesis 3A*: Taxonomic richness increases
185 functional diversity that promotes trait selection. *Hypothesis 3B*: In opposition to 3A,
186 taxonomic diversity can increase stochasticity in community assembly due to an
187 increase in functional redundancy (Rosenfeld 2002), priority effect (Fukami 2015), and
188 a reduction in the average population sizes (Walter *et al.* 2021). *Hypothesis 4A*:
189 Dispersal limitation by spatial isolation of communities fosters stochasticity due to a
190 reduction in taxonomic and functional diversity and an increase in the random variation

191 in species recruitments (Chase 2010; Orrock & Watling 2010; Fisher & Mehta 2014;
192 Fukami 2015; Leibold & Chase 2018; Siqueira et al. 2020). *Hypothesis 4B*: In
193 opposition to 4A, isolated communities select species with good-dispersal traits and
194 reduce the strength of mass effect, enhancing the trait-performance association (Leibold
195 et al. 2004; Ai et al. 2013; Borthagaray et al. 2015; Leibold et al. 2019). *Hypothesis 5*:
196 Heterogeneity and low frequency of disturbance relax environmental filters, at least in
197 temporary ponds, reducing the strength of trait selection (Cadotte & Tucker 2017).

198

199 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

200 **2.1 Study system**

201 The metacommunity of plants evaluated in this study is located in a flat landscape
202 surrounded by hills, where a maximum of 61 ponds, every year, are filled with water in
203 winter and dry out in summer in the same spatial locations (Figure 2). The study area is
204 located in the Castillos Lagoon basin, in the Rocha department, Uruguay (34°15'16.9 "S
205 53 ° 58'51.6 "W; 5-8 meters altitude). According to the Köppen-Geiger climate
206 classification system, it belongs to the category of 'Cfa' climate, characterized by a
207 humid subtropical climate with hot summers and mild to cool winters (Kottek et al.,
208 2006). In the study area zone, during the study period (2005-2018), the mean annual
209 temperature was 16.6 ° C (mean minimum monthly temperature of 11.3 °C, mean
210 maximum monthly temperature of 21.9 °C), with extreme recorded temperatures of -9.0
211 ° C (exceptionally in spring) and 39.8 ° C in summer. The mean annual precipitation
212 was about. 1287 mm, with an annual minimum and maximum of 1676 and 847 mm,
213 respectively; while the mean annual wind velocity was 9.2 km/h coming predominantly
214 from the east, with gusts of approximately 44 km/h (Meteomanz 2020). Temporary
215 pond soil textures range from clay to silt to loam, with a predominance of loam and clay

216 loam soils. The land cover in the study area is classified, based on satellite imagery, as
217 grasslands, flooded grasslands, and agriculture or pasture (Baeza *et al.* 2022).

218 Temporary ponds are distributed along two rural establishments dedicated to extensive
219 cattle raising and ecotourism.

220 Every spring since 2005, these ponds have been sampled equidistantly using 20x20 cm
221 quadrants on the major axis. On average, five quadrants were sampled in most ponds.
222 However, to account for the range of pond areas, which exhibits differences in several
223 orders of magnitude (from 6.6 m² to 24,673 m²) when the quadrants were closer than
224 two meters, the number of sampled units was reduced, and if the quadrants were more
225 than 10 meters apart, then the number of sampled units was increased (Arim *et al.* 2011;
226 Piñeiro-Guerra *et al.* 2014; Borthagaray, Berazategui & Arim 2015; Rodriguez-Tricot &
227 Arim 2020). As a consequence, while five sample units were collected in most ponds,
228 few or more quadrants were sampled in smaller and larger ponds, respectively (range 2
229 to 22, see Supplementary Figure 1). The depth does not follow a smooth increase from
230 the border to the centre of the ponds. In fact, shallow and deeper areas alternate along
231 the bottom, even forming small dry islands (see Figure 2). Differences in island density
232 and spatial variation in depth within ponds represent one of the main sources of
233 heterogeneity, which was related with the assembly of animal species in this
234 metacommunity (Borthagaray, Berazategui & Arim 2015; Rodriguez-Tricot & Arim
235 2020). Consequently, a border-centre stratification of sample units was not considered.

236 All biomass of the aboveground plant was removed and identified in the laboratory. The
237 area where the biomass was removed represented a negligible fraction of the pond area,
238 and the locations of the quadrants were not sampled repeatedly over years. A pond was
239 excluded from the present analyzes because it corresponded to a permanent wetland.

240 Thus, we had a total of 599 spatial-temporal communities corresponding to 60 ponds

241 sampled during 22 campaigns over 14 years. During this time, M. Arim was responsible
242 for all surveys and V. Pinelli led field sampling since 2014. The taxonomic
243 classification was first led by C. Fagúndez, who was progressively replaced by V.
244 Pinelli. External evaluation was ensured to classify the samples when necessary. In the
245 database conformation, we never had an abrupt replacement in the conformation of the
246 researchers and students involved in the field sampling and laboratory processing,
247 taking care to maintain protocols among sampling events. No permission for fieldwork
248 with plants is required in the study area.

249

250 **2.2 Trait data**

251 A species-by-trait matrix was constructed from a review of the literature and direct
252 observations (Supplementary Table 1). In Table 1, the list of traits considered is
253 presented, introducing their description and functional roles. Different traits related to
254 dispersal strategy, competitive ability, drought resistance strategy, life history, and
255 tolerance to stress were considered. Correlation in the occurrence of traits is expected,
256 and a reduction in this multicollinearity is important for functional, ecological
257 syndromes, and statistical reasons, lack of independence. Consequently, a principal
258 coordinate analysis (PCoA) based on Gower distances was performed with the trait
259 matrix using the ape package in R (Paradis & Schliep 2018). The community-weighted
260 means and the community-weighted variances were estimated for each PCoA axis.
261 These values are the mean and variance, respectively, of the community trait values -
262 PCoA axes -estimated among all the individuals sampled in the community. The
263 average and variance in community-weighted traits are expected to systematically
264 change along environmental gradients in response to trends in the selection profile
265 (Shipley 2010; Loranger *et al.* 2018). For the estimation of community aggregated

266 moments, abundances were estimated by adding species occurrences for each pond
267 during the study period.

268

269 **2.3 Community Assembly by Trait Selection (CATS)**

270 In CATS, trait states are related to the relative abundance of each species from a
271 regional pool via selection coefficients estimated with abundance-trait regressions
272 (Warton, Shipley & Hastie 2015). Metacommunity abundances are used as a prior
273 distribution that is incorporated as an offset into the model (Warton, Shipley & Hastie
274 2015). Regression parameters represent 'selection coefficients' that relate species
275 abundances or occurrences with traits (Shipley, Vile & Garnier 2006; Shipley 2010). If
276 the community is neutrally assembled, then species abundances are independent of
277 species traits (Shipley, Paine & Baraloto 2012; Shipley 2014a). On the contrary, if all
278 variation in abundance is explained by species traits, then the community is
279 deterministically assembled by the selection of traits. Consequently, for the range of
280 functional traits considered, the fraction of the variation in species abundances related to
281 drift represents a continuous index between 0 and 1 of the assembly of communities by
282 trait selection or stochastic processes, respectively (Shipley, Paine & Baraloto 2012;
283 Shipley 2014a). The decomposition of deviance from the CATS analysis was proposed
284 as a method to directly estimate the role of species traits, the mass effect of the
285 metacommunity composition, and the stochastic drift in the assembly of communities.

286 For each local community, a CATS analysis was performed (Shipley, Vile & Garnier
287 2006; Shipley 2010; Warton, Shipley & Hastie 2015). Basic information collected on
288 the structure of the community was the occurrence of species observed in the
289 metacommunity among the quadrants sampled. Consequently, we use logistic
290 regressions to relate the presence or absence of species in each pond with species

291 traits—species scores on the PcoA axis. The abundance of species in the
292 metacommunity was used as an offset variable (Warton, Shipley & Hastie 2015) and
293 was estimated by adding observed occurrences to the sampling units among all the
294 ponds. This offset captures the mass effect of metacommunities on local abundances
295 (Shipley 2014b). In addition, the offset accounts for the effect of differences in species
296 abundances on local occurrences, representing a mechanistic alternative to considering
297 species identity as a random variable. The positions of each species along each of the
298 first four PCoA axes based on traits were used as composite trait predictor variables in
299 the CATS regressions. Because species performance can be non-linearly related to the
300 trait axis, we also considered a quadratic term (Loranger *et al.* 2018). A logistic
301 regression was fitted for each pond considering the sampling time as a random effect—
302 package “glmmTMB” of R (Magnusson *et al.* 2017). We also considered a time-
303 autoregressive model with a mixed effect of sampling date. However, these models
304 frequently failed to converge and, when they did, had a lower performance than a model
305 without an autoregressive component (see Supplementary Table 2). The values of the
306 logistic model parameters relating the probability of species occurrence with the
307 composite trait variables of each species (that is, the PCoA axis scores) were calculated
308 and related to pond area, heterogeneity, hydroperiod, and connectivity.

309

310 **2.4 Environmental gradients**

311 Community connectivity was quantified by two centrality metrics, degree and
312 closeness, estimated on a percolation graph, which is a network that connects all ponds
313 with the minimum linkage Euclidean distance required for linkage (Borthagaray *et al.*
314 2015). Degree centrality (direct connectivity hereafter) is the number of direct
315 connections of a local pond with other ponds, and closeness centrality (global

316 connectivity hereafter) is the reciprocal of the average distances of a local pond with all
317 the other ponds in the metacommunity, representing metrics of direct and global
318 connectivity, respectively (Economato & Keitt 2010). The area of the pond was estimated
319 as the area of an oval using the length of the major and minor axes of the ponds. The
320 variation in plant cover between ponds is surpassed by the range of pond areas spanning
321 several orders of magnitude, supporting the use of area as a proxy of community size
322 (Berazategui 2012). In the following, we refer to the area of the pond in the statistical
323 analysis and the size of the community in the discussion. The hydroperiod was
324 estimated as the proportion of sampling times with water for sampling carried out
325 between 2006 and 2009, when the ponds were visited several times. Heterogeneity was
326 estimated as the number of 'islands', emergent mounds above water level, per meter of
327 the main and minor axes of the ponds (see Figure 2). The average environmental values
328 during the sampling time were used.

329 A Principal Coordinates Analysis with flexible path adjustments of the distance matrix
330 was used to resume the range of community assemblies observed in the metacommunity
331 (Shipley 2021). Community scores on the ordination axes were associated with
332 environmental gradients: area, heterogeneity, hydroperiod, and isolation.

333

334 **2.5 Deviance partition**

335 To estimate the fraction of the variation in community abundance associated with
336 population stochastic drift, deviance decomposition was performed (following Shipley,
337 Paine & Baraloto 2012; Shipley 2014a). Following the methods in Shipley (2014a), the
338 variation in the local abundance of species associated with drift can be estimated by
339 fitting two different models and retaining the associated pseudo R-squared values. The
340 first model estimated the explained variance $R^2(u)$ in a model without traits or

341 metacommunity information. This model was the “maximally uninformative” model,
342 which assumed an equal effect of all species of the metacommunity on the local
343 assembly—using a uniform distribution as offset—and a random permutation of the
344 trait vector (the average pseudo R-squared from 200 randomizations was retained). This
345 randomization provided a permutation estimation of model bias— $R^2 > 0$ by chance
346 (Shipley 2014a). The second pseudo R-squared $R^2(m, t)$ was estimated from a model that
347 used observed metacommunity abundances as offset and observed species traits as
348 independent variables. $1 - R^2(m, t)$ represents the fraction of abundance not explained by
349 species traits or metacommunity abundance, that is, the fraction of variation in species
350 abundances explained by drift (after Shipley 2014a). However, this drift estimate must
351 be standardized by the expected drift estimate from the first model (Shipley 2014a).
352 Thus (after Shipley 2014a):

353
$$R_{Drift}^2 = \frac{1 - R^2(m, t)}{1 - R^2(u)}$$

354 where the variation in abundances associated with drift was estimated for the 60
355 communities. This estimate was contingent on the set of traits considered, providing an
356 upper limit estimation of drift (Shipley 2010). The estimated drifts (R_{Drift}^2) for each
357 pond was retained.

358

359 **2.6 Environmental determinants of the strength of trait selection**

360 Hypotheses about the causal structure that connected environmental conditions,
361 diversity, and the niche-neutral assemblage of communities (Figure 1) were evaluated
362 with path analyses (Shipley 2016). The amount of variation in abundance explained by
363 drift was related to local conditions—pond area, heterogeneity, and hydroperiod—, the
364 isolation of the communities, and functional and taxonomic diversity—e.g. species

365 richness. Functional diversity was quantified by a set of community-level
366 complementary indices with the FD package (Laliberté & Legendre 2010; Laliberté,
367 Legendre & Shipley 2014). We calculated the observed richness, number of
368 functionally singular species (sing.sp), functional richness (Fric), functional evenness
369 (Feve), functional diversity (Fdiv), and functional dispersion (Fdis). A best subset
370 model selection was used to identify variables that were significantly associated with
371 the strength of stochasticity in community assembly (McLeod & Xu 2014). As indices
372 of functional diversity could be mutually associated and also associated with the
373 taxonomic richness (De Bello *et al.* 2021), we only considered indices with less than a
374 0.8 correlation between them and with the taxonomic richness.

375 Path analyses were performed with the lavaan package in R (Rosseel 2012). The
376 purpose of these analyzes was to evaluate the set of hypotheses presented in Figure 1
377 and the emergent causal structure. Path analyses were performed using the original
378 variables and considering quadratic transformations of variables when theoretical
379 expectations involved both positive and negative associations, for example, for the
380 effect of area and connectivity on stochasticity in community assembly. The final model
381 was identified by progressively deleting nonsignificant variables. Indirect effects were
382 obtained from the product of the path coefficients on the sequence of links along the
383 path leading from one variable to other (Shipley 2016). The overall effect of each
384 variable on the strength of stochasticity in community assembly was estimated with the
385 sum of all direct and indirect effects (Shipley 2016). Bollen-Stine bootstrapping was
386 used to evaluate the fit of the model and estimate parameter significance (Rosseel 2012;
387 Shipley 2016). After the plausible model was identified, all variables were z-
388 standardized for visualization, and their standardized coefficients were reported. All the

389 data and functions used in the article are presented in Dryad:

390 <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.12jm63z32>.

391

392 **3. RESULTS**

393

394 **3.1 Trait gradients**

395 The first four axes of the PCoA on species traits retained 88% of the original variability
396 of traits between species. We retained these four axes because considering additional
397 axes only produced a small increase in explained heterogeneity, not capturing large
398 sources of trait differences between species (Figure 3A). The average and variance in
399 the traits weighted by the community changed systematically along the environmental
400 gradients (Supplementary Figures S2). These trends support the main role of trait
401 selection in the response of the community to environmental conditions (Figure 3B and
402 Supplementary Figures S3). The first PCoA of species traits essentially captured a
403 gradient in dispersal traits and adaptation to aquatic environments, with winged seeds
404 and drought-tolerant species at one extreme and vegetative spread and intolerance to
405 drought at the other. The representation of this axis in communities presented a
406 systematic response to environmental gradients in area, heterogeneity, and hydroperiod.
407 Large and persistent ponds favour tall plants with life cycles adapted to a persistent
408 water environment that is dry only during summer (Figure 3B). Small ponds with short
409 hydroperiods and internal heterogeneity favour vegetative spread species that can
410 survive in a seed bank and adult plants that are tolerant of pond drying. The second
411 PCoA axis tended to represent alternative strategies for drought tolerance, from plant
412 resistance, where adult individuals survive a drought period, to seed resistance in which

413 adults die, but seeds survive (Figure 3A). The representation of these traits was
414 associated with the hydrodynamic regimen of the pond. The third axis was associated
415 with a gradient from cosmopolitan, small and not tolerant to anaerobiosis, to native,
416 large and aquatic species that were preferred in more heterogeneous environments
417 (Figure 3A). Connectivity and internal heterogeneity were associated with changes in
418 the representation of these traits. Finally, the fourth axis was associated with
419 reproduction in the summer period, after the ponds dried, or in spring at the end of the
420 pond hydroperiod. The hydroperiod of the pond and heterogeneity determined the
421 representation of these traits (Figure 3B). Community weighted variance decreased with
422 direct connectivity along the four axes and, in general, was positively correlated with
423 spatial heterogeneity (axes two and four) and hydroperiod (axes two, three, and four).
424 On the other hand, the ordination of ponds on the basis of species representation also
425 reflected the potential effects of connectivity, area, hydroperiod, and heterogeneity in
426 the trait-mediated assembly of communities (Figure 3C).

427

428 **3.2 Stochasticity and trait selection**

429 Local communities were located along a niche-neutral gradient, with large
430 differences in the amount of variation in species occurrences explained by traits or drift
431 ($0.22 < R_{Drift}^2 < 0.84$). This scenario involved a gradient from communities close to a
432 niche assemblage—in which 22% of the variation in species occurrences was explained
433 by drift and the other 78% of the variation was explained by species traits—to
434 communities close to a neutral assembly where species occurrences were loosely related
435 with species traits—84% of the variation in species occurrences was explained by drift
436 and only 16% explained by traits. In particular, this neutral-niche gradient was well
437 explained by environmental variables and community diversity (Figure 4). Among

438 diversity indices, taxonomic richness, the number of functionally singular species, and
439 functional richness presented correlations greater than 0.8, only considering taxonomic
440 richness in subsequent analyzes. The selection of the best subset model selection
441 retained taxonomic richness and functional dispersion (Fdis) as variables related to
442 stochasticity in community assembly. These variables were included as proxies of
443 taxonomic and functional diversity in the path analyses. Similarly, direct connectivity
444 (degree) and global connectivity (closeness) were mutually correlated, and direct
445 connectivity was superior when explaining stochasticity in community assembly, so it
446 was used in the path analyses.

447 The first hypothesized causal structure for path analyses included a direct effect
448 of area, connectivity, hydroperiod, heterogeneity, richness, and functional dispersion on
449 drift; a direct effect of area on richness, heterogeneity, hydroperiod, and functional
450 dispersion; and a direct effect of connectivity, hydroperiod, and heterogeneity on
451 functional evenness. This model was poorly supported by the data ($\chi^2_9=21.4$, P: 0.011)
452 and pointed to a nonsignificant effect of the hydroperiod, which was removed in
453 subsequent analyses. The next model, without hydroperiod, was supported by the data
454 but presented a nonsignificant effect of area on drift and a nonsignificant effect of
455 heterogeneity on functional dispersion. Furthermore, only the quadratic value of
456 connectivity was significantly linked to drift. A second model without these links was
457 well supported by the data (see Figure 4). Although the data supported a model with a
458 direct effect of the area on drift, this effect was not significant and did not improve
459 model performance ($\Delta AIC < 2$).

460 The overall effect of the area on stochasticity was positive (standardised effect:
461 0.44). However, it should be noted that this overall effect was composed only of indirect
462 paths and that these involve both positive effects mediated by taxonomic richness (0.27)

463 and spatial heterogeneity (0.15) and a negative effect mediated by functional diversity (-
464 0.13). Connectivity had a positive indirect effect on stochasticity mediated by the
465 increase in functional diversity (0.09) and presented a non-linear direct relationship with
466 a maximum positive effect at intermediate connectivity. Functional dispersion and
467 taxonomic richness presented similar direct effects on stochasticity (0.31 and 0.35
468 respectively). Finally, spatial heterogeneity presented the largest direct effect,
469 increasing the stochasticity community assembly (0.53).

470

471 **4. Discussion**

472 The determinants of neutral flat-fitness landscapes versus performance-trait associations
473 are a long-standing controversy in biology (Carroll 2001) and other disciplines (Cobey
474 & Lipsitch 2012; Arthur & Sibani 2017). Throughout the twentieth century, theories
475 that attempted to understand the evolution of species traits (Wright 1932), molecular
476 biochemistry (Monod 1971) and population genetics (Kreitman 1996), as well as the
477 ecology of individuals (Losos 2017) and population dynamics (Royama 1992),
478 converged on the view of a balance between chance and necessity as the determinant of
479 most biological phenomena. Stimulated by Stephen Hubbell's controversial neutral
480 theory (Vellend *et al.* 2014), community ecology was probably one of the last areas of
481 biology in which this view was accepted. As the drift-selection balance has become
482 accepted in community assembly, identifying the scenarios that promote a more neutral
483 or trait-assembled community has emerged as a central aim in this field (Shipley, Paine
484 & Baraloto 2012; Vellend *et al.* 2014; Tucker *et al.* 2016; Janzen *et al.* 2017; Bosc *et al.*
485 2019; Leibold *et al.* 2019; Mitchell *et al.* 2019; Ulrich *et al.* 2019; Viana & Chase
486 2019). Attempting to address this question, we focused on the essential differences
487 between stochastic drift and niche assembly: a connection between species traits and

488 species performance (Hubbell 2001; Shipley 2010; Vellend 2016; Leibold & Chase
489 2018).

490 We found evidence supporting the main role of traits in community assembly,
491 with local communities covering a large gradient from stochastic to deterministic
492 assembly. Ponds are ephemeral systems with environmental conditions that strongly
493 change over time and space (Richardson *et al.* 2022). Therefore, they are considered
494 extreme environments inhabited by species adapted to these conditions (Biggs, Von
495 Fumetti & Kelly-Quinn 2017; Hill *et al.* 2021). Taxonomic assemblies in ponds were
496 generally proposed to emerge from the selection of adapted species on the basis of
497 indirect evidence (but see Cunillera-Montcusí *et al.* 2020). With the conceptual and
498 methodological framework of Community Assembly by Trait Selection (CATS), we
499 explicitly evaluated the role of traits in diversity patterns along environmental gradients.
500 As expected, the large pool of plant species observed in this metacommunity is made up
501 of organisms with traits that ensure its viability in aquatic or semi-aquatic
502 environments. However, a large diversity of traits was observed covering different life
503 histories, dispersal strategies, tolerance to drought, and competitive capacities. Our
504 results indicate that this functional diversity at the metacommunity level is probably
505 supported by different selection regimens among different ponds (Figures 3 and
506 Supplementary Figure S3). Although all of the ponds considered here are ephemeral,
507 the small and isolated ponds are covered with water for a shorter period of time and
508 then dry out and refill during winter and spring. The opposite is true for large ponds,
509 which have deeper and persistent water. The selected traits represented the ability of the
510 species to survive the drying of the ponds during the water-covered phase, the life
511 histories coupled with the water cycle of the pond, the size of the organism and different
512 aspects of the dispersal strategies (Figure 3 and Supplementary Figures S2 and S3). The

513 effect of these environment-dependent selection regimens (Supplementary Figure S3) is
514 evidenced in the change in community weighted means but also in the community
515 weighted variances—CWV (Supplementary Figure S2). The increase in CWV may
516 result from a reduction in the strength of environmental filters and also from the action
517 of disruptive selection in which an alternative combination of traits between species can
518 provide a good solution for a selective regimen. Supporting an increase in recruitment
519 and persistence of species with connectivity, the mass effect, CWV was positively
520 associated with connectivity. However, other environmental variables closely related to
521 CWVs presented both increase or reduction in the variability of traits depending on the
522 PCoA axis considered, pointing to the existence of complex selective scenarios
523 operating in the study system. All these results support niche assembly mechanisms,
524 which, however, do not preclude a significant role for stochastic drift in species
525 abundances. This reinforces the importance of empirically identifying and theoretically
526 understanding the strength of drift in community assembly.

527 The representation of species in different communities was well explained by
528 the interaction between environmental conditions and species traits (Figure 3,
529 Supplementary Figures S2 and S3). However, the role of traits in community assembly
530 presented a large variation between ponds. This variation was largely explained by the
531 environmental gradients proposed by theory as putative determinants of trait selection
532 versus stochastic drift in community assembly (Figure 1). Explicitly, connectivity
533 (Orrock & Watling 2010; Fisher & Mehta 2014; Fukami 2015; Siqueira *et al.* 2020b),
534 taxonomic diversity (Chase 2010; Fukami 2015), functional diversity (Shipley 2010;
535 Enquist *et al.* 2015), and environmental filters (Cadotte & Tucker 2017) are here
536 identified as direct determinants of the balance between selection and stochasticity
537 (Figure 4). However, while stochasticity could be reduced in large communities (Orrock

538 & Watling 2010; Fisher & Mehta 2014; Fukami 2015; Siqueira *et al.* 2020b), we did not
539 find evidence supporting this expectation. In this sense, the existence of a direct path
540 between the pond area and stochasticity was not supported by the path analyzes (Figure
541 4). In the following paragraphs, we further consider the empirical evidence about
542 determinants of the trait-selection versus stochastic drift balance and the putative
543 mechanisms involved.

544 Taxonomic and functional diversities are both consequences and determinants of
545 the strength of trait selection and community drift. Trait selection operating through
546 environmental filters reduces the set of species and traits in a local community and
547 consequently reduces taxonomic and functional diversities (Cadotte & Tucker 2017). In
548 contrast, when trait selection involves limits to species similarity, the local functional
549 diversity is expanded (Adler, HilleRisLambers & Levine 2007; Rodriguez-Tricot &
550 Arim 2020). The positive association between diversity and drift is supported by our
551 results, considering that taxonomic diversity is closely associated with indices that
552 represent functional richness. However, to produce a change in the relative abundance
553 of species, selection must act on individuals with different functional traits (Shipley
554 2010). However, we found that functional and taxonomic diversity significantly
555 promoted stochasticity in community assembly. Several mechanisms predicted these
556 positive effects (Figure 1), but functional diversity, which is the substrate for selection
557 processes, was expected to directly dampen stochasticity in community assembly. In
558 this context, we emphasize that increasing functional diversity may promote the
559 existence of alternative solutions, combinations of traits, for a single selection regimen,
560 determining functional redundancy between species with different traits. As a
561 consequence, the abundance-trait association could be reduced, which reflects the
562 increase in stochasticity but not necessarily a reduced role of traits in species

563 performance. Clearly, this is a result that motivates further attention on theoretical and
564 methodological grounds. Finally, large communities have substantially high taxonomic
565 diversity and physical heterogeneity but low functional diversity, evidencing both
566 positive and negative effects of area on stochasticity. These alternative effects may
567 produce variations in the observed area-stochasticity association among studies, guided
568 by differences in the functional and taxonomic diversity of different systems. Similarly,
569 when these paths are mutually balanced, a weak or no association may be reported
570 despite the strong effects involved.

571 Our results support the hypothesized trend from niche-based to drift-based
572 community assembly along the gradient of pond connectivity (Brown & Swan 2010; Ai
573 *et al.* 2013; Borthagaray *et al.* 2015). In particular, the humped effect of connectivity on
574 stochasticity supports both positive and negative effects. Isolated ponds with low
575 connectivity play a greater role in trait selection, probably due to a reduced mass effect
576 and a consequent strong connection between species traits and species performance
577 (Brown & Swan 2010; Ai *et al.* 2013; Borthagaray *et al.* 2015). This contradicts the
578 expectation of a larger role for stochasticity in isolated communities (Orrock & Watling
579 2010; Gilbert & Levine 2017; Vannette & Fukami 2017). A higher dispersal rate
580 incoming to more connected ponds may determine a rise in mass effects, attenuating the
581 role of species traits in local performance, also increasing the stochasticity in
582 community assembly because of species redundancy (Leibold *et al.* 2004; Brown &
583 Swan 2010; Ai *et al.* 2013; Borthagaray *et al.* 2015). However, trait-selection has again
584 an influential role in community assembly along those ponds with higher connectivity
585 levels. This increase in the traits-performance relationship could be determined by the
586 availability of species with a more optimal combination of traits for the selection
587 scenario. This availability is not necessarily represented in the index of functional

588 diversity considered here and elsewhere (De Bello *et al.* 2021). These results add to
589 those of a number of studies that support community isolation as a major determinant of
590 community structure, to a much larger extent than previously thought (Borthagaray,
591 Arim & Marquet 2012; Borthagaray, Berazategui & Arim 2015; Brown *et al.* 2017;
592 Borthagaray *et al.* 2023).

593 The spatial heterogeneity of the ponds is identified as a main determinant of the
594 strength of stochasticity in the assembly of plant communities. We consider that this
595 effect is determined by attenuation of environmental filters by heterogeneity (Cadotte &
596 Tucker 2017). Heterogeneity was here estimated as the density of 'islands' (see Figure
597 2), a metric associated with spatial variation in depth, soil texture, and nutrients
598 (Piñeiro-Guerra *et al.* 2014). Furthermore, these islands introduce barriers for animal
599 movement, plant vegetative growth, spatial refuges, and patches of conditions that
600 favour species coexistence (Borthagaray, Berazategui & Arim 2015; Rodriguez-Tricot
601 & Arim 2020). The increase in island density should promote the recruitment of more
602 species with different functional traits, attenuating the traits-occurrence relationship and
603 fostering the role of stochastic drift in species abundances. The previous points can
604 explain the increase in stochasticity with the spatial heterogeneity of the ponds, but not
605 the observed reduction in the community weighted variance with heterogeneity
606 (Supplementary Figure S2). This reduction in traits variance may support the action of
607 stronger environmental filters, a scenario in which the increase in stochasticity can also
608 be related with neutral aggregation of species (Holt 2006; Scheffer & van Nes 2006).
609 For example, when only plant species with similar traits are able to recruit and the
610 subsequent relative abundances are determined by drift because the variation for the
611 action of trait-selection was depleted by the filter. We finally note that the connection
612 between the strength of environmental filters and the role of traits in community

613 assembly is expected, but has been rarely reported, also demanding further theoretical
614 and empirical attention (Vellend 2016; Cadotte & Tucker 2017; Keddy & Laughlin
615 2021).

616 Any approach to identifying the mechanisms behind biodiversity patterns has
617 strengths and limitations. The main potential limitation of our selected approach and
618 studies on functional diversity in general is the contingency of the estimated patterns on
619 the set of species traits considered (Shipley 2010; De Bello *et al.* 2021). In this sense,
620 our estimation of stochastic drift should be interpreted as an upper bound, since
621 variation in abundance unexplained by traits may include hidden niche mechanisms
622 related to unmeasured traits. However, it should be noted that the set of traits considered
623 herein covers a wide range of potential niche mechanisms related to dispersal (e.g., seed
624 size, shape, shape and dispersal syndrome), competition (e.g., vegetative spread, plant
625 height), herbivory (e.g., leaf size), and local filters (e.g., anaerobiosis and drought
626 tolerance, nitrogen fixation) and proxies for several traits, such as the Sculthorpe and
627 Raunkiaer classification or photosynthetic path. In fact, the representation of these traits
628 and their effect on species occurrences systematically changed along the environmental
629 gradients of the pond (Figures 3 and 4 and Supplementary Figures S2 and S3).

630 An explicit focus on higher-level processes, selection versus drift, was indicated
631 as an important step in the construction of a general theory (Hubbell 2001; Shipley
632 2010; Vellend 2016). In this context, a focus on the amount of variation in abundance
633 accounted for by traits (Shipley 2014b) has three main advantages for the empirical
634 analysis of niche-stochastic gradients in community assembly. *First*, it provides a direct,
635 continuous, and clear quantification of the role of trait selection and stochastic drift in
636 community assembly. Therefore, these simple approaches may overcome tests based on
637 particular patterns, such as species abundance distribution (see also van der Plas *et al.*

638 2015; Tucker *et al.* 2016; Leibold & Chase 2018). *Second*, the estimated drift from the
639 CATS deviance partition assesses the role of stochasticity independently of the specific
640 niche or neutral mechanism in the assemblage of communities (Shipley 2010; Warton,
641 Shipley & Hastie 2015). *Third*, the method of deviance partitioning is directly based on
642 metacommunity mechanisms that attempt to be quantified (Shipley, Vile & Garnier
643 2006; Shipley 2010; Shipley, Paine & Baraloto 2012; Shipley 2014a; Shipley 2014b;
644 Warton, Shipley & Hastie 2015). In summary, a focus on the trait abundance
645 association may significantly expand the empirical evaluation of the determinants of
646 niche mechanisms and of the relative role of neutral and niche processes in community
647 assembly.

648

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660

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662

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667

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904

905 **Figure legends**

906

907 Figure 1. Hypothesized direct and indirect determinants of trait-mediated mechanisms
908 versus stochasticity in community assembly. Hypotheses that predict opposite patterns
909 are indicated by the same number and different letters (H3A and H3B; H4A and H4B).

910

911 Figure 2. Study system. Ponds are formed in land depressions that fill with rainwater
912 every autumn and winter and dry at the end of spring. Ponds are indicated in blue. The
913 inset graph is the percolation network, a graph that connects all ponds with a minimum
914 linkage distance, used to estimate pond connectivity. The images highlight the
915 heterogeneity in the areas and physical structure of the ponds, and the inset numbers in
916 the images correspond to the pond id. The presence and density of small islands
917 represent a main source of heterogeneity.

918

919 Figure 3. Diversity of plant traits and their representation in temporary ponds. A:
920 Principal coordinates analysis (PCoA) summarizing the multicollinearity in species
921 traits. Traits with large association with the PCoA axes are indicated within the plots. B:
922 The average (CWM) and variance in community-weighted traits systematically changed
923 along the environmental gradients (Supplementary Figures S2), and only significant
924 trends in CWM are presented here. These three sets of results indicate the existence of a
925 large functional diversity in the species pool (A), the potential action of trait-selection
926 processes in community assembly determined by environmental conditions (B and
927 Supplementary Figure S2), resulting in gradients in the species composition of
928 communities (C).

929

930

931 Figure 4. Hypothesized causal relationships among environmental gradients (pond area,
932 heterogeneity, and isolation), taxonomic and functional diversity, and the relative role
933 of niche (trait-mediated) versus stochasticity (drift) in the assembly of communities.

934 The numbers in the boxes represent standardized effects; Pz is the link probability from
935 the maximum likelihood fitting, and P.boot values are the probabilities estimated from
936 Bollen-Stine bootstrapping, which are robust in terms of sample size and deviation from
937 normality assumptions. R-squared values within the variable boxes indicate the amount
938 of variation in the variable that is explained by the path model.

939

940 **Table Legends**

941 Table 1. Description of traits of plant species and their functional implications.

942

943 **Supplementary material**

944 Supplementary Figure S1. Median number of sampling units collected in each pond
945 arranged in increasing pond areas.

946

947 Supplementary Figure S2. Community-weighted means and community-weighted
948 variances of the species traits (first four PCoA axes) along gradients of pond areas,
949 connectivity, heterogeneity, and hydroperiod.

950

951 Supplementary Figure S3. Logistic regression coefficients for linear and quadratic terms
952 associated with species traits, PcoA axes. The red curves indicate expectations for the

953 GAM regressions and confidence intervals. The systematic trends observed indicate
954 changes in selection scenarios along the environmental gradients.

955

956 Supplementary Table 1. Species trait database. An xlsx file with species traits in the
957 first column, followed by 100 columns for each of the species recorded in the study
958 system.

959

960 Supplementary Table 2. Comparison of autoregressive models with a covariance
961 structure of Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (ou), which provides the same result as an
962 autoregressive structure when data are evenly spaced, but also consider data with
963 uneven time separation—some ponds were not observed at all sampling times. Note that
964 'ou' models, indicated but with the suffix 'ar' for autoregressive, frequently failed to
965 converge. When converged, their performance in terms of AIC or BIC was inferior in
966 comparison to models without a time dependence.

967

968 Supplementary material 1. Species occurrence database. An xlsx matrix with columns
969 year, month, pond and sample unit and the occurrence of 100 species.

970

971 Supplementary material 2. Environmental variables. An xlsx file with the columns:
972 Pond.id: numeric code that identifies ponds, X: latitude coordinates, Y: longitude
973 coordinates, Major diameter: length of pond major diameter; minor diameter: length of
974 pond minor diameter, Shape: major/minor diameter ratio; islands: number of emergent
975 dry monticules per meter of major and minor diameter, log. Area: logarithmic base 10
976 of the pond area, log. Volume: logarithmic base 10 of the volume of the pond, mean.

977 Depth: average depth of the pond, Sd. Depth: standard deviation of the depth of the
978 pond, CV. Depth: coefficient of variation of the pond depth, Hydroperiod: proportion of
979 surveys in which the pond had water (2006-2009), Degree: number of direct
980 connections of a pond with other ponds, Closeness: reciprocal of the mean of the
981 minimum distance of the pond to all other ponds in the metacommunity.

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984 Figure 1
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Figure 3

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996 Figure 4

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1000 Table 1
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 1002

Trait	Description	Attributes
Status	Origin, distribution and propagation tendency in the regional flora ¹	Native, endemic, naturalized, a cosmopolitan, introduced
Seed size	Main axis length ²⁻⁵	No seeds, <1mm, 1-3mm, 3-5mm
Seed shape	Geometric approximation of the seed form ²⁻⁵	No seeds, spherical, ellipsoid, obovate, elongated, winged
Dispersal syndrome	Dispersal agents correlated to seed morphological characters ²⁻⁴	Barochory, anemochory, zoochory
Vegetative spread	Capacity of production of clones through rhizomes, stolons or bulbs ²⁻⁶	Yes, no
Leaf size	Leaf area ²⁻⁴	Leafless, <2cm ² , 2-5cm ² , >5cm ²
Habit	Mode of vegetative growth ²⁻⁶	Prostrate, erect, caespitose, rosette
Sculthorpe	Occupation of microhabitats within the pond. Position on the edge-center and bottom-surface gradients ⁷	No hydrophyte, amphibious, rooted, emergent, rooted with floating leaves, free and submerged, free rooted and submerged, free with floating leaves, free and submerged
Plant height	Vegetative height of adults, in vertical direction ²⁻⁵	Continuous, in cm. Maximum vegetative height
Stem length	Vegetative length of the main plant axis (stems) in any direction ²⁻⁵	Continuous, in cm. Maximum vegetative length
Persistence	Life span ^{2-5, 7}	Annual, biennial, perennial
Reproductive period	Season when flowering begins ²⁻⁵	Spring, summer, autumn, winter
Stem type	Stem woodiness ²⁻⁶	Herbaceous, semi-woody, woody
Nitrogen fixation	Increased nitrogen fixation by association with nitrogen fixing bacteria ^{2-5, 7}	Yes, no
Anaerobiosis tolerance	Tolerance to low or null oxygen content levels ^{6,7}	Yes, no
Drought tolerance	Tolerance to low soil water content levels ^{6,7}	Yes, no
Photosynthetic path	Metabolic carbon fixation pathway ⁷	C3, C4
Raunkiaer	The relation of the perennating tissue (meristematic tissue that remains inactive during the unfavourable season) to the ground surface ^{6,7}	Therophyte, cryptophyte, hemicryptophyte, chamaephyte, phanerophyte.

¹ Darwinion web 2019; ² Lombardo 1982; ³ Lombardo 1983; ⁴ Lombardo 1984; ⁵ Alonso Paz 1997; ⁶ Field observations; ⁷ Cornielissen et al 2003; ¹⁰ Pérez-Harguindeguy et al 2013

1003

1004 Supplementary Figure S1
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Supplementary Figure S2

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